

SPACE ASTROMETRY

The detailed equation of condition in Step 1: Effects of orientation and tilt of the slit plate.

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1. Introduction

In a note of 76-10-19 I described a three-step procedure for deriving the astrometric parameters of stars from great-circle scans according to Option A. The basic feature of this procedure is that, in Step 1, we find the projection of the five astrometric parameters of a star onto a specific great circle, apart from an additive constant within the group of scans or orbits considered. The constants of the various groups are found in Step 2, and in Step 3, finally, the results of the previous steps for a specific star at different epochs are combined to yield the astrometric parameters of that star. The equations of condition given in that note (Eq. (4)) were very simplified as they include only two instrumental constants: the basic angle and the scale value at the grid.

In the present note I first derive strict formulae for a central (gnomonic) projection onto an arbitrarily oriented grid, then I make a number of simplifications and approximations, assuming that the basic alignment and dimensional accuracy is of the order of 10^{-3} , at worst, and that terms contributing less than 0.0001 are negligible. It is shown that this leads to six independent instrumental constants to be determined. The equation of condition corresponding to (4) in the previous note is given.

It is also shown that the finite average density of stars (about one per square degree) only permits a finite factor of positional amelioration in one step (about 100x). Hence at least two steps of iteration are foreseen, since the starting accuracy of stellar positions (including systematic errors) is probably about 0.5 . The first step in this iteration can probably be much simplified, e.g. by ignoring the parallaxes.

2. Systems of Coordinates

I will use two rectangular systems of coordinates that are fixed to the satellite: the xyz-system, defined by the optical centre of the telescope and the two flat mirrors, and the $\xi\eta\zeta$ -system on the slit plate, in which the coordinates of the stellar images are in the first instance expressed. Transformation between these two systems involves six constants, corresponding to three translations and three rotations. Together with the basic angle, they define the instrumental constants. However, because only relative measurements are made in one direction in the slit plane (i.e. only angles between stars are measured), and because of the relatively small field of view, it is not possible to separate all the seven constants. In practice, we have only six instrumental constants.

2.1. The xyz-system

This system is similar to that used in the MDS (see Fig. 1), but is more strictly defined as follows:

Origin O = the optical centre of the telescope. Since we assume no field distortion, i.e. central or gnomonic projection, this point is well defined.

The z-axis is parallel to the intersection of the two mirror planes; seen from the tip of $\hat{z}$ the instrument rotates clock-wise as it scans the sky. However, the instantaneous axis of rotation generally deviates from the z-axis. If $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$ are unit vectors normal to the mirror planes, we have
$$\hat{z} = (\hat{p} \times \hat{f}) / |\hat{p} \times \hat{f}| .$$

The x-axis bisects the angle between $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$:
$$\hat{x} = (\hat{p} + \hat{f}) / |\hat{p} + \hat{f}| .$$

The y-axis is such that xyz is a right-hand system:
$$\hat{y} = \hat{z} \times \hat{x} .$$

2.2. The basic angle

The basic angle γ is twice the angle between $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$:
$$\cos \frac{\gamma}{2} = \hat{p} \cdot \hat{f} .$$

2.3. The $\xi\eta\zeta$ -system

Origin is an arbitrary point on the slit plane.

The ξ -axis is normal to the slit plate; light propagates through the plate approximately in the $+\xi$ direction.

The η -axis is normal to the slits and directed so that the η coordinate of a stellar image increases during scanning.

The ζ -axis is parallel to the slits: $\hat{\zeta} = \hat{\xi} \times \hat{\eta}$

2.4. The strict formulae for transformations between the systems

Let P be the point where the x-axis intersects the slit plane. Its coordinates are

$$P: (x, y, z) = (F, 0, 0), \text{ or } (\xi, \eta, \zeta) = (0, \eta_0, \zeta_0) \quad (1)$$

(cf. Fig. 1). Thus, F, η_0 , and ζ_0 determine the translations between the systems. Let us then assume that the $\xi\eta\zeta$ -system translated to origin O is obtained from the xyz-system by rotation

1. the angle ψ around the z-axis, then
2. the angle φ around the y-axis, and finally
3. the angle $180^\circ + \theta$ around the x-axis.

The full transformation from xyz to $\xi\eta\zeta$ is then given by

$$\begin{pmatrix} \xi \\ \eta - \eta_0 \\ \zeta - \zeta_0 \end{pmatrix} = \underline{M} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x - F \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\underline{M} = \begin{pmatrix} m_{11} & m_{12} & m_{13} \\ m_{21} & m_{22} & m_{23} \\ m_{31} & m_{32} & m_{33} \end{pmatrix} =$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi \cos \varphi & \sin \psi \cos \varphi & -\sin \varphi \\ -\cos \psi \sin \varphi \sin \theta + \sin \psi \cos \theta & -\sin \psi \sin \varphi \sin \theta - \cos \psi \cos \theta & -\cos \varphi \sin \theta \\ -\cos \psi \sin \varphi \cos \theta - \sin \psi \sin \theta & -\sin \psi \sin \varphi \cos \theta + \cos \psi \sin \theta & -\cos \varphi \cos \theta \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

For the reverse transformation from $\xi\eta\zeta$ to xyz, we notice that $\underline{M}$ is orthogonal and hence $\underline{M}^{-1} = \underline{M}^t$.

It is now easily seen that central projection of a point $Q = (x, y, z)$ onto the slit plane ($\xi = 0$) yields a point Q' with coordinates

$$\eta = \eta_0 + F \frac{m_{33}y - m_{32}z}{m_{11}x + m_{12}y + m_{13}z}$$

$$\xi = \xi_0 + F \frac{-m_{23}y + m_{22}z}{m_{11}x + m_{12}y + m_{13}z} \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, when (η, ξ) of Q' is given, we obtain (x, y, z) of Q through

$$x = F + m_{21}(\eta - \eta_0) + m_{31}(\xi - \xi_0)$$

$$y = m_{22}(\eta - \eta_0) + m_{32}(\xi - \xi_0)$$

$$z = m_{23}(\eta - \eta_0) + m_{33}(\xi - \xi_0). \quad (5)$$

The direction of the vector $\overline{OQ}$ is specified either by (4) or (5); we can also introduce angles σ and τ , such that $90^\circ - \tau$ is the angle between $\overline{OQ}$ and $-\hat{z}$, and σ is the corresponding azimuth angle in the $+\eta$ direction (see Fig. 1). Thus

$$\tan \sigma = -y/x$$

$$\tan \tau = -(z/x) \cos \sigma. \quad (6)$$

3. Measurement of the angle between two stars

Let $\hat{s}_p$ and $\hat{s}_f$ be unit vectors towards two stars which are simultaneously in the p- and f-field, respectively. As a first approach to the more general problem I shall discuss the determination of the angle u between the stars from observations of (η, ξ) , assuming that the instrumental constants are known. The angle u is defined by $\cos u = \hat{s}_p \cdot \hat{s}_f$.

In Fig. 2 is outlined the arrangement of angles and coordinates along a great circle on the sky, passing through $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$. I call this the principal great circle (p.g.c.). Spaced by $\gamma/4$ we have along the p.g.c. the points $\hat{r}_p, \hat{p}, \hat{x}, \hat{f},$ and $\hat{r}_f$, where $\hat{r}_p$ and $\hat{r}_f$ are images of $\hat{x}$ reflected in $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$, respectively. The coordinates σ and τ are similarly reflected by $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$ into σ_p, τ_p and σ_f, τ_f , respectively. Also, $\hat{s}_p$ and $\hat{s}_f$ are mirrored by $\hat{p}$ and $\hat{f}$ in $\hat{S}_p$ and $\hat{S}_f$, respectively.

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By measuring (η, ξ) of $\hat{S}_p$ and $\hat{S}_f$, and applying (5) and (6), we obtain coordinates (σ, τ) of the two stars, as if they were measured in systems $\sigma_p \tau_p$ and $\sigma_f \tau_f$, respectively. It is then easy to see that the angle between the two stars, as seen from +z, is

$$v = \gamma - \sigma_p + \sigma_f, \quad (7)$$

and that u is then found from

$$\cos u = \sin \tau_p \sin \tau_f + \cos \tau_p \cos \tau_f \cos v. \quad (8)$$

As τ_p and τ_f are small compared to v and u , we see from (7) and (8) that errors in σ_p and σ_f have direct influence on u , whereas errors in τ_p and τ_f have less influence on u via (8). However, the required accuracy of τ_p and τ_f is still rather high. Differentiation of (8) gives, approximately,

$$du = - \operatorname{cosec} u \left[(\tau_f - \tau_p \cos v) d\tau_p + (\tau_p - \tau_f \cos v) d\tau_f \right]. \quad (9)$$

If the errors in τ_p and τ_f are due mainly to an erroneous zero-point ζ_0 , we can put $d\tau_p = d\tau_f = d\tau$, $(\tau_p + \tau_f)/2 = \tau$, and obtain

$$du = - 2\tau \tan \frac{v}{2} d\tau. \quad (10)$$

If $\tau = 25'$ and $v = 60^\circ$, we must require $|d\tau| < 0.06$ in order that $|du| < 0.0005$. However, the rms value of τ is $\sqrt{6}$ times less, which gives us $d\tau_{\text{rms}} < 0.15$.

The implication of (10) is that the position of z on the sky must at any moment be known with an accuracy of about 0.15 . The position of $\hat{z}$ on the sky is derived from ζ -measurements of stars by means of the inclined slits at the beginning and the end of the slit plate. In order to see how often such measurements are needed it would be very useful to have an estimate of the power spectrum of the movement of the axis.

4. Expansion and simplification of the formulae for σ and τ

Eqs. (5) and (6) give

$$\tan \sigma = (A + B\eta + C\xi)/(1 + D\eta + E\xi), \quad (11)$$

where $A, B, C, D,$ and E are independent constants which can be derived

from $F, \eta_0, \zeta_0, \theta, \varphi$, and ψ . In a first approximation they are:

$$A = \eta_0/F, \quad B = 1/F, \quad C = \theta/F, \quad D = \psi/F, \quad E = -\varphi/F. \quad (12)$$

Series expansion of (11) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \tan \sigma = & A + (B - AD)\eta + (C - AE)\zeta + (-BD + AD^2)\eta^2 + (CD - BE + 2ADE)\eta\zeta + \\ & + (-CE + AE^2)\zeta^2 + (BD^2 - AE^2)\eta^3 + (CD^2 + 2BDE + 3AD^2E)\eta^2\zeta + \\ & + (2CDE + BE^2 - 3ADE^2)\eta\zeta^2 + (CE^2 + AE^3)\zeta^3 + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

For estimating the sizes of the various terms, let us assume $F \sim 1600$ mm; $\eta, \zeta \sim 10$ mm; $\eta_0, \zeta_0 \sim 1$ mm; $\theta, \varphi, \psi \sim 10^{-3}$ rad ($\sim 3'$). We then have

<u>term</u>	<u>size</u> (milliarcsec)
1	10^5
η	10^6
ζ	10^3
η^2	8
$\eta\zeta$	8
ζ^2	$8 \cdot 10^{-3}$
η^3	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$\eta^2\zeta$	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
$\eta\zeta^2$	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$
ζ^3	$5 \cdot 10^{-8}$

It thus suffices to include the first five terms:

$$\tan \sigma = c_1 + c_2\eta + c_3\zeta + c_4\eta^2 + c_5\eta\zeta; \quad (14)$$

moreover, it is easily shown that $c_1 - c_5$ are completely independent.

However, σ is used differentially only, as in (7). With $\sigma = \tan \sigma - \frac{\tan^3 \sigma}{3}$ we obtain (with some obvious approximations)

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma = & (c_1 - \frac{1}{3}c_1^3) + (c_2 - c_1^2c_2)\eta + c_3\zeta + (c_4 - c_1c_2^2)\eta^2 + \\ & + c_5\eta\zeta - \frac{1}{3}c_2^3\eta^3. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In differential measurements, the first term is eliminated, and we still have five significant terms. However, they are, effectively, no longer independent. The last term is, approximately,

$$-\frac{1}{3} c_2^3 \eta^3 \approx -\frac{1}{3} (\eta/F)^3, \quad (16)$$

which is of the order of 15 milliarcsec. This term can be computed at once, and we have only the coefficients of the other four terms free for a least-squares adjustment. Hence we can write (7) in the form

$$v = \delta + e_1(\eta_f - \eta_p) + e_2(\zeta_f - \zeta_p) + e_3(\eta_f^2 - \eta_p^2) + e_4(\eta_f \zeta_f - \eta_p \zeta_p) - \frac{1}{3} F^{-3}(\eta_f^3 - \eta_p^3). \quad (17)$$

Similarly, we can expand the expression for $\tan \tau \sec \sigma$. Since the accuracy of τ required is about 60 milliarcsec, we conclude that three terms are sufficient:

$$\tan \tau \sec \sigma = e_5 - e_2 \eta + e_1 \zeta. \quad (18)$$

The six instrumental constants are δ and $e_1 - e_5$.

5. The position of $\hat{z}$ on the sky

As mentioned at the end of Section 3 we need to know the position of $\hat{z}$ on the sky with a precision of about 0.15 in order to apply eq. (8) and compute u from v . For most stars we observe only η , and not ζ . When the position of $\hat{z}$, (λ_z, β_z) , and the approximate position of the star, (λ', β') , are known, we have

$$\sin \tau = \sin \beta' \sin \beta_z + \cos \beta' \cos \beta_z \cos (\lambda' - \lambda_z). \quad (19)$$

$\hat{z}$ describes a path on the sky which we can set as

$$\beta_z(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m b_i B_i(t), \quad \lambda_z(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m l_i L_i(t), \quad (20)$$

where $B_i(t)$ and $L_i(t)$ are suitable functions (e.g., polynomials or trigonometric functions) and b_i and l_i are constants to be determined. Conventional iterative least-squares improvement of b_i and l_i gives the

following equation of condition for each ζ measurement:

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \left[\frac{\partial (\sin \tau)}{\partial \beta_z(t)} B_i(t) \Delta b_i + \frac{\partial (\sin \tau)}{\partial \lambda_z(t)} L_i(t) \Delta l_i \right] = \sin \tau_{\text{obs}} - \sin \tau_{\text{comp}} \quad (21)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial (\sin \tau)}{\partial \beta_z(t)} = \sin \beta' \cos \beta_z(t) - \cos \beta' \sin \beta_z(t) \cos (\lambda_z(t) - \lambda'),$$

$$\frac{\partial (\sin \tau)}{\partial \lambda_z(t)} = - \cos \beta' \cos \beta_z(t) \sin (\lambda_z(t) - \lambda'). \quad (22)$$

6. The complete equation of condition

In Step 1 of the three-step procedure we set up the equation of condition for the angles projected onto a specific great circle. However, we cannot simply use the p.g.c., since we consider in this step a group of (say) 5 - 10 orbits as a unit, and during that time the p.g.c. changes a great deal ($\hat{z}$ moves about 1°). Let us instead introduce a reference great circle (r.g.c.) for each such group of orbits, with its pole (λ_r, β_r) fixed among the stars, onto which all angles in the equation of condition are projected. The pole (λ_r, β_r) should preferably be about the average position of $\hat{z}$ during the group of orbits, but the precise choice of it is arbitrary.

In the equation of condition, we shall compare the true angle w between two stars, projected onto the r.g.c. (i.e., the angle between the stars when seen from $\hat{r} = (\lambda_r, \beta_r)$), and the angle w' computed from the approximate coordinates of the two stars. Below, the prime will always denote quantities or vectors derived from approximate coordinates. Introducing the angles u' , ρ'_p , and ρ'_f , according to

$$\cos u' = \hat{s}'_p \cdot \hat{s}'_f, \quad \sin \rho'_p = \hat{s}'_p \cdot \hat{r}, \quad \sin \rho'_f = \hat{s}'_f \cdot \hat{r}, \quad (23)$$

we have

$$\cos w' = (\cos u' - \sin \rho_p' \sin \rho_f') / (\cos \rho_p' \cos \rho_f'). \tag{24}$$

The formula for w is, strictly,

$$\cos w = (\cos u - \sin \rho_p \sin \rho_f) / (\cos \rho_p \cos \rho_f), \tag{25}$$

where u, ρ_p , and ρ_f are defined analogously to u' , ρ_p' , and ρ_f' in (23). However, since ρ_p and ρ_f are not known, we have to use the approximate formula

$$\cos w = (\cos u - \sin \rho_p' \sin \rho_f') / (\cos \rho_p' \cos \rho_f'). \tag{26}$$

We thus introduce an error in w which is analogous to the error in u caused by errors in τ_p and τ_f , and we can estimate the error with a formula analogous to (9) or (10). For instance, if ρ_p' and ρ_f' are of the order of 1° (i.e. the stars are about 1° from the r.g.c.), we cannot tolerate errors in ρ_p' and ρ_f' exceeding about 0.025 , in order that the error in w should not exceed 0.0005 . This, of course, makes an iterative solution necessary. On the average, the requirements are slightly less stringent, but if a group contains stars within $\pm 1^\circ$ from the r.g.c., we can hardly expect to improve the positional accuracy of the stars by more than a factor 100 in one iteration.

An iterative solution is desirable also for other reasons. For instance, it is perhaps not possible to determine all the instrumental constants satisfactorily for each group of orbits; in a later iteration we can use smoothed and interpolated values of the "constants" and solve for other types of corrections instead, e.g. field corrections.

Before I continue I summarise the formulae used to compute w and w' when η_p and η_f are observed and $\hat{z}$, $\hat{r}$, $\hat{s}_p'$, and $\hat{s}_f'$ are given.

$$\sin \tau_p' = \hat{z} \cdot \hat{s}_p', \quad \sin \tau_f' = \hat{z} \cdot \hat{s}_f', \tag{27a, b}$$

$$\sin \rho_p' = \hat{r} \cdot \hat{s}_p', \quad \sin \rho_f' = \hat{r} \cdot \hat{s}_f', \tag{27c, d}$$

$$\cos u' = \hat{s}_p' \cdot \hat{s}_f', \quad \cos u = \sin \tau_p' \sin \tau_f' + \cos \tau_p' \cos \tau_f' \cos v, \tag{27e, f}$$

$$v = \gamma + e_1(\eta_f - \eta_p) + e_2(\zeta_f - \zeta_p) + e_3(\eta_f^2 - \eta_p^2) + e_4(\eta_f \zeta_f - \eta_p \zeta_p) - \frac{1}{3} F^{-3}(\eta_f^3 - \eta_p^3), \tag{27g}$$

$$\zeta_p = (\tan \tau'_p \sqrt{1 + (\eta_p/F)^2} - e_5 + e_2 \eta_p) / e_1, \quad (\text{similarly for } \zeta_f), \quad (27h, i)$$

$$\cos w' = (\cos u' - \sin \rho'_p \sin \rho'_f) / (\cos \rho'_p \cos \rho'_f), \quad (27j)$$

$$\cos w = (\cos u - \sin \rho'_p \sin \rho'_f) / (\cos \rho'_p \cos \rho'_f). \quad (27k)$$

To obtain the equation of condition in Step 1 we have to differentiate $w - w'$ with respect to γ and $e_1 - e_5$. We then have to take into account that a change in e_5 has no influence on ζ_p or ζ_f via (27h-i), but influences τ'_p and τ'_f only, via the adopted position of $\hat{z}$, which of course will depend on the value of e_5 . With this in mind, we derive the following equation of condition:

$$\begin{aligned} w - w' = dw_f - dw_p + \frac{\cos \tau'_f \cos \tau'_p \sin v}{\cos \rho'_f \cos \rho'_p \sin w} & \left[d\gamma + (\eta_f - \eta_p) de_1 + \right. \\ & + (\zeta_f - \zeta_p) de_2 + (\eta_f^2 - \eta_p^2) de_3 + (\eta_f \zeta_f - \eta_p \zeta_p) de_4 - \\ & \left. - (\tau'_f + \tau'_p) \tan \frac{v}{2} de_5 \right]. \quad (28) \end{aligned}$$

When there are two stars from the same field (p- or f-field) measured simultaneously, the same equation of condition applies, only with the term $d\gamma$ excluded.

The coefficient

$$\cos \tau'_f \cos \tau'_p \sin v / (\cos \rho'_f \cos \rho'_p \sin w)$$

deviates from unity with at most approximately $0.0008/\sin^2 v$, or 0.001 for $v = 60^\circ$. Thus, since we have to make an iterative solution anyway, we can replace it by 1 for a pair of stars from the different fields ($v \sim 60^\circ$), and by $\sin v / \sin w$ for a pair of stars in the same field of view ($v \sim 0^\circ$).

Fig 1.

Fig. 2.

